

Experimental UX assessment of the SOULSS platform: a neurophysiological approach

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In the context of the SOULSS project a preliminary platform testing was performed for assessing its usability. This experimental UX assessment was designed to understand user interaction and identify areas for improvement.

1. The assessment methodology

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To gain a comprehensive understanding of the user experience, participants were engaged in specific tasks while being monitored with advanced neurophysiological tools.

- **Mindtooth Touch (EEG):** This device measured brain activity to assess mental workload, stress, and attention levels.
- **Shimmer GSR3+:** A wristband was used to collect data on heart activity (PPG) and skin sweating (EDA). Data from these sensors is currently being processed and will be finalized by the end of April.
- **Tobii Eye Tracker 5:** This tool tracked ocular movements to analyze user behavior through metrics like fixation count (FC), time to first fixation (TFF), and mouse clicks (MC).

Participants were instructed to perform three tasks: free navigation on the homepage, following a tutorial module, and creating a basic course.

2. Key findings

The usability of the tutorial was assessed by focusing on three key elements: navigation options, text content, and video content.

- **Navigation Options:** This element caused the highest levels of mental workload and stress. Eye-tracking data corroborated this, showing low fixation counts and high mouse clicks, suggesting the navigation was not immediately obvious. This indicates that the navigation element could be made more visible to improve its functionality.
- **Text Content:** The text content received a medium fixation count, indicating that while it was viewed, its effectiveness could be enhanced. Highlighting or summarizing the text could improve user engagement.
- **Video Content:** The video content proved to be sufficiently visible and easy for users to understand.

In parallel, the assessment of the course creation process focused on two aspects: the „New course” button and the spoiler options.

- **„New course” button:** This button was not easily visible to participants. This led to high levels of stress and mental workload, as well as a high time to first fixation and a high number of mouse clicks, indicating that users struggled to locate it.
- **Spoiler options:** The functionality of the spoiler options was not easy for users to understand. As a result, they also generated high stress and mental workload. Enhancing their description within the tutorial could help users better understand their purpose.

In conclusion, this preliminary testing has provided critical insights into the user experience of the SOULSS platform. The results highlight specific areas for improvement, particularly concerning the visibility of key features and the clarity of certain functionalities. These findings will be used to enhance the platform’s usability and create a more intuitive experience for all users.

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